

Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure and Financial Performance: The Moderating Role of Environmental Performance

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ABSTRACT: Purpose: Scholars actively consider the growing trend of corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure and eco-friendly environment initiatives by firms. Since the beginning of the 1950s, scholars have been actively involved in exploring the concept of CSR. Thus, many studies have been conducted to conceptualize, operationalize and develop the framework of CSR. The objectives of the study are twofold: firstly, this study inspects the impact of CSR disclosure on firm performance (FP). Secondly, we also explore the interactional effect of environmental performance on the relationship between CSR disclosure and FP.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The study uses regression analysis approach. Using content analysis to measure CSR disclosure with five dimensions; employee, consumer, supplier, government, and society. EP was measured through the EIndex. In this study, FP is measured by using two indicators: Tobin's Q (market-based measure) and earnings per share (EPS) (accounting-based) measures. The annual reports of the companies are the source of the data. Purposeful sampling was used to select 70 manufacturing firms from the PXS 100 index for this study. The time frame covered by the panel study is from 2017 to 2021, and two firm performance measures, Tobin's Q and EPS, will be used.

Findings: The empirical findings show that CSR disclosure significantly influences Tobin's Q and EPS. Moreover, results indicate the interactional role of EP in the relationship between CSR disclosures

Originality: No empirical study was found with the moderation effect of the environmental performance between the relationship of CSR disclosure and firm performance with the sample size of 100 index manufacturing firms.

Practical Implementation: Practitioners will find consistency in empirical findings to improve the social and financial performance of the firms.

Social Implementation: This study helps society consider firms with high social and environmental performance, as high social and environmental performance leads to high financial health.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure, Environmental Performance, Financial Performance; Tobin's Q; Earnings Per Share

1. Introduction

In the previous decades, the issue of sustainability became imperative, and the shareholders highly considered the firm's social activities. With the beginning of the 21st century, firms' engagement in corporate social responsibility has become the organization's primary concern globally. Scholars' explanation gives strong evidence of the activities related to CSR that revolve around sustainability and satisfying concerned people (Homburg et al., 2013). In the corporate social responsibility domain, many researchers focus on the factors related to the determination of CSR rather than measuring CSR disclosure (Eng & Mak, 2003; Khlif et al., 2015).

Furthermore, Davis (1973) explains corporate social responsibility as a strong motive that not only focuses on the marginal net benefit to the firm but also contributes to society's welfare, which leads toward the firm's long-term survival. Firms can attain competitive benefits over their competitors by investing in CSR activities (Wahba & Elsayed, 2014). Scholars' study indicates the higher financial performance of firms with CSR activities rather than firms with no CSR activities (Lambertini & Tampieri, 2015). Besides this, some researchers explore the link between corporate social responsibility and the firm performance of different countries with different sectors. However, the researchers find mixed findings as some results show a positive link, some indicate a negative relationship, and some show no association (Alexander & Buchholz, 1978; Orlitzky et al., 2003).

Organizations and scholars pay attention to CSR activities as attaining sustainability is important. Social Investment Forum, 2014 shows that around 4 trillion dollars have been spent by 8,000 firms from 160 countries on CSR. The companies which cover the proportion of 500 Poor's and Standard organization have brought CSR reports, which increased by 20 per cent in 2011 and 70 per cent in 2013 (Wang et al., 2018). Some scholars reveal how firms "do well by doing good" (Kang et al., 2016; Orlitzky et al., 2003); however, researchers have found that the link between corporate social responsibility and company performance is not simple. Some studies indicate a positive connection between CSR and firm performance enables firms to attain a competitive advantage for the organizations (Bernal- Conesa et al., 2017; Farooq et al., 2017; Mishra & Modi, 2016), but contrary to this finding, some studies indicate that firms meet agency and financial cost occurred due to engagement in corporate social responsibility activities which results in the low financial performance of the company (Di Giuli & Kostovetsky, 2014; Ting & Yin, 2018). To address this conflict, scholars consider the contingency perspective to elaborate on the influence of CSR on the financial performance of organizations (Kim et al., 2018; Ting & Yin, 2018).

Scholars find that the influence of CSR on financial performance is moderated through competitive action (Kim et al., 2018). The scholars find that the influence of Corporate social responsibility on financial performance is moderate through the excessive control rights of controlling shareholders (Ting and Yin, 2018). Some scholars state in their study that the expenditures incurred due to research and development (R&D) and advertising indicate a contingent effect and used these two fundamental functions for value creation and firm value appropriate determination (Mizik & Jacobson, 2003), and influence on the connection between CSR and firm performance. The organization pays more

attention to environmental and social concerns as the public has an upward trend. The organization provides information related to the environmental and societal activities of the firms (Hamrouni et al., 2020) in such ways which indicate firms' obligations other than firms' contractual obligations (Choi et al., 2010), legal and technical prerequisites (Carter, 2005), as well as an economic concern (Turker, 2009). As organizations' operation integrates with social and environmental issues (Bocquet et al., 2017), corporate social responsibility becomes a crucial element of the business strategy (Choi et al., 2010).

The economy of Pakistan falls in the developing countries; thus, the ownership structure, operations, and CEOs of Pakistani firms fall in developing countries, which may be different from the developed countries. The economic growth of Pakistan is comparatively slow from other countries. Firm growth can be enhanced through the substitute growth model called "CSR activities" as stakeholders pay more attention to CSR activities. The reason behind Pakistan's low economic growth is facing many issues, such as an unstable economy, political instability, poor health and education development, energy crises, and corruption prevailing in the country. Furthermore, the organization works in an environment where people's living standards are low as they have insufficient incomes, the quality of products is low, violation of human rights due to severe corruption, and child labor is the most notified thing. Now the increase in environmental and water pollution is considered an important issue because of the mishandling of waste material by the organization (Ehsan et al., 2018).

In addition, awareness of CSR is less in Pakistan. Thus, small firms adopt CSR activities less than large firms in Pakistan (Waheed, 2018). Moreover, the investigation related to corporate social responsibility and environment is associated with growth, and the implementation of CSR in the firms of Pakistan is at the initial level (Gamerschlag et al., 2011), specifically the execution of CSR. Therefore, it needs to be considered CSR from the perspective of Pakistan to enhance the requirements of CSR and its importance and awareness of CSR for both government authorities and societies. In Pakistan, the trend of corporate social responsibility is new, as the CSR general ordinance developed in 2009 by the Security and Exchange Commission of Pakistan (SECP). Firms need to disclose information about corporate social responsibility According to the Security and Exchange Commission of Pakistan ordinance every year. The SECP directs the firms to implement a well-described corporate social responsibility policy in the firms' vision statement, which indicates the CSR's obligation and framework with the code of ethics and the development of the business plan defined by the SECP (SECP, 2013). Hence, this study leads toward exploring factors regarding CSR activities and how firms adopt such activities by keeping all the concerns of CSR by the Pakistani firms.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

Although researchers pay close attention to corporate social responsibility, the previous studies indicate mixed results on the connection between corporate social responsibility and firm performance. The discrepancy highlighted underscores the critical nature of conceptualizing CSR, as emphasized in previous literature (Wood, 2010). It reveals that there is no uniformity in the application of CSR practices worldwide, and

furthermore, there is a lack of a proper shared global concept of CSR. This variability and lack of consensus can pose challenges for organizations implementing CSR strategies effectively across different regions and contexts (Ağan et al., 2016).

The growing demand by the stakeholders for sustainability and eco-friendly services and products forces firms to adopt corporate social responsibility activities (Van Beurden & Gössling, 2008). The different published research on the notion of corporate social responsibility indicates the definitions of CSR that organizations must CSR activities while making environmental management strategies to meet the societies' expectations (Gössling & Vocht, 2007; Saeidi et al., 2015).

Baumgartner (2014) claimed that Corporate social responsibility can be defined as integrating social and environmental characteristics into corporate activities. Freeman (1984) presents the well-known stakeholders' theory 1984 which proposes that a particular group of people should be focused on by the manager who influences and influences the firms' activities. Freeman (1984) states that, concerning the social aspect, the 'production view' is less complex than the 'managerial view', and the organization is likely to act responsibly to meet the expectations of consumers, government, and investors and responsible for managing employees to build the sustainable value of firms. The connection between CSR and firm performance can be interpreted through two important theoretical approaches. According to the classical view, also familiar as the shareholder view, Friedman (1970) debates that employees and executive managers are only responsible for enhancing the shareholders' wealth. The market mechanism is neglected when firms focus on CSR instead of maximizing profit, preventing firms from maximizing allocated resources.

Orlitzky (2015) acknowledged the shareholder perspective and claimed that, while CSR is helpful in some cases, it ultimately weakens the foundation of liberty, property rights, and the free market. The other important theoretical approach is the opposite of the shareholder view. Freeman (1984) states his point of view that the organization's reputation is enhanced through the fulfilment of the stakeholders' expectations, which also positively affects the financial performance of the firms. Freeman argued his point of view by presenting the stakeholders' theory that shareholders are part of the stakeholders, whether they are internal or external voters (Ruf et al., 2001). Unavoidable social cost reduces shareholders' value when firms meet the worst conflicts of stakeholders (Ruf et al., 2001). The maximization of the shareholders' profits is also prioritized for stakeholder-oriented organizations while meeting the stakeholders' expectations (Mishra & Suar, 2010).

Furthermore, according to the agency theory, engagement in corporate social responsibility activities incurs additional costs for the firms and is considered an expense for shareholders, resulting in a decline in profit (Cronqvist et al., 2009; Pagano & Volpin, 2005). The research results indicate the negative connection between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and financial performance conducted in Brazil (Crisóstomo et al., 2011). Barnea and Rubin (2010) explore the influence of corporate social responsibility on corporate value. The arguments of their study are based on agency theory. They state that agency costs are incurred when managers spend a lot of money on corporate social responsibility activities to secure their careers. Shin et al. (2011) explore the relationship

between donation expenditure and corporate value, and the findings initially show a positive correlation. Later, they find a negative relationship between CSR and FP after an appropriate level.

Friede et al. (2015) found in their study that environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria and FP (financial performance) of the firms positively correlated; from the mid of 1990s, the empirical findings remain positive between ESG and FP. Financial performance is enhanced through higher CSR (Crifo et al., 2016; Rodriguez-Fernandez, 2016), and sustainability leads toward enhancing profit through these initiatives of firms (Kuzey & Uyar, 2017). Researchers claim in their studies that although many studies show mixed empirical findings from three decades, researchers tended to explore a positive correlation between human resources, green initiative suppliers and customer dimensions, and financial performance (Crifo et al., 2016). So, considering the above literature, this study formulates the first hypothesis mentioned below.

H1: CSR Disclosure significantly influences the Financial Performance of the firms.

The impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure on environmental performance has been actively discussed in academia for the past decades. One perspective by the researcher support of voluntary disclosure theory, which is an economics-based theory that suggests that organizations have the incentive to disclose good characteristics of the firm (Cho et al., 2012) and adoption of proactive strategy by the firms indicates the higher environmental performance by considering the stakeholder issues (Clarkson et al., 2008). Furthermore, the information asymmetry will reduce with more disclosure between managers and external stakeholders, resulting in better financial transparency of firms. Researchers find that corporate social responsibility disclosure positively influences environmental performance, confirmed through empirical evidence (Mahmoudian et al., 2021; Tadros & Magnan, 2019; Uyar et al., 2020).

In their study, Tadros and Magnan (2019) state that firms disclose higher CSR information with better environmental performance. Uyar et al. (2020) note that global logistics firms, with a sample size of 2012 to 2018, disclose more CSR reports with better CSR performance. Mahmoudian et al. (2021) find a significant connection between GHG emissions reporting and performance by taking the US S&P 500 firms as a sample. The GHG emissions reporting positively influence performance and indicate better performance. While the other perspective shows, the socio-political theories view, just like legitimacy theory, which indicates that firms' operation is done within the boundaries of the society by demonstrating CSR disclosure. The firm used this as a strategy to manage the news of the low environmental performance of the firm. Legitimacy theory indicates that managers usually use sustainability disclosure to influence the organization's especially bad perception. Thus, resulting in poor performance with more disclosure of information.

Many studies confirm this negative relationship between disclosure and performance (Cho et al., 2012; Gray, 2006; Patten, 2002). Cho et al. (2012) note that, with a sample size of 500 US firms, disclosure of information regarding environmental capital spending leads toward poor environmental performance compared to disclosed firms. Generally, the

perspective of voluntary disclosure theory and legitimacy theory is different, and scholars find mixed, non-conclusive empirical evidence. Some studies indicate that both theories should be reconciled by dividing the firms into two categories such as low-quality and high-quality disclosures (Hummel & Schlick, 2016; Tadros & Magnan, 2019).

The firm makes revenue and product costs from environmental management. Many scholars conducted studies to empirically test the connection between environmental performance and firm performance to check whether additional income is more than the costs through different studies, and in 2010, a paper of review studies was published. In their study, Zeng et al. (2010) find that cleaning the environment and engaging in cleaner production activities positively affect the firm's performance, exploring evidence from Chinese firms. Explore the poor financial performance of Spanish firms with ISO 14001 certification, calculated through the sale and ROA (Heras-Saizarbitoria et al., 2011). Iwata and Okada (2011) find better financial performance measured through return on invested capital, return on assets and return on investment with reduced GHG, while waste emissions did not enhance the FP in Japanese firms.

Nishitani (2011) states that the value of Japanese firms is enhanced by improving productivity and increasing demand by implementing the ISO 14001 environmental management system. Hatakeda et al. (2012) debate on the connection between GHG and ROA can be reduced while there is a positive association if firms control GHG emissions through environmental management. Razafindrambinina and Sabran (2014) explore that return on assets is not influenced by the environmental aspects of corporate social responsibility. Qi et al. (2014) find that industry-level ROA (return on asset) decreases with sulfur dioxide emissions per unit of industry value in the industrial sectors of China. Scholars find a positive association of environmental innovation with returns on equity and ROA (return on asset) in Polish and Hungarian firms (Przychodzen & Przychodzen, 2015). Thus, based on the above discussion, this study formulates the following hypothesis to check the simultaneous influence of environmental performance and CSR on FP.

H2: Environmental Performance strengthens the associations between CSR Disclosure and the Financial Performance of the Firms.

Conceptual Model

The study's conceptual model in Figure 1 shows the independent variable (CSR disclosure) and dependent variable (financial dependent). Figure 1 also shows that environmental performance (moderating variable) strengthens the influence of CSR disclosure and FP.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Table I. Review of the Empirical Findings of Previous Research on the Connection among CSR Disclosure, Environmental Performance & Financial Performance

Findings	Period	Country	Methodology	Authors
Study reveals the negative relationship between CSR and FP	2001–2006	Brazil	The study used Lagged effects methodology	(Crisóstomo et al., 2011)
Empirical evidence supports a positive correlation between CSR and FP	2009–2015	China	The study used a Paired-samples t-test & Regression analysis methodology	(Jia, 2020)
The study shows that CSR and FP are positively correlated	1990–2007	Spain	The event study technique to test the hypotheses	(B. Casado-Díaz et al., 2014)
The study reveals higher FP through the CSR engagement	2011–2018	Global markets (120 countries)	The study used univariate & multivariate analyses to check the association.	(Kuzey et al., 2021)
The study's findings indicate a positive relationship between ESG and FP and CEO POWER	2004–2013	UK	The study used Heckman's two-stage estimator & an instrumental.	(Li et al., 2018)
The simultaneous effect of EP & CSR disclosure significantly influences ROE & ROA	2012–2013	Indonesia	The study used causal study methodology and regression analysis	(Angelia & Suryaningsih, 2015)

3. Methodology

Sample and Procedures

In this study, panel data is used for empirical analysis as different entities have been selected for a period of 5 years. Quantitative data is collected through the firm's annual reports of the PXS 100 index manufacturing firms from 2017 to 2021. The empirical analysis is obtained through the Stata software. The purposive sampling technique with a sample size of 70 manufacturing firms of PXS 100 index firms where observation is 350. Principal component analysis (PCA) is used to create one index for CSR disclosure and environmental performance. The panel regression analysis has been done to find the association between CSR disclosure and FP.

Measurements of Variable

Corporate Social Responsibility

The data collection source in the previous study is usually from the annual report of the companies (Gray et al., 1995; Neu et al., 1998). Information about the organization is provided on the company-developed web page as the internet is widely used all over the world (Wanderley et al., 2008). Scholars use the “content analysis” method to calculate Corporate social responsibility (Branco and Rodrigues, 2008). Karaibrahimoglu (2010) uses five dimensions to calculate CSR: supplier, employee, consumer, government, and society. As content analysis is used in this study, we assign 1 for the existence of the information on CSR; otherwise, in case of the absence of information, we assign 0.

Financial Performance

In the previous literature, scholars used Perceptual-based, accounting-based (EPS, ROA, ROE), and market-based (Tobin’s Q) proxies to calculate the FP of the firms (Orlitzky et al., 2003).

Market-based performance (Tobin’s Q)

Scholars used Tobin’s Q to measure the firm’s financial performance, which indicates the firm’s market valuation concerning assets used in the organization (Rodgers et al., 2013). Tobin’s Q, a financial performance measure, also indicates the public’s trust in an organization and the long-term profitability of firms (Marti et al., 2015). The researchers claim to measure the financial performance through Tobin’s Q, reflecting the effect of CSR in medium-term and long-term periods (Pekovic & Vogt, 2021).

Accounting-based performance (EPS)

Some of the perspectives of previous literature argue that the positive impact of CSR and FP is not a worldwide phenomenon but an industry or region-specific issue (Jo et al., 2015). Corporate social responsibility positively correlated with the FP of the companies measured through the accounting-based proxy (Marti et al., 2015). The short-term financial performance of the firms is measured in accounting-based performance as compared to Tobin’s Q (Pekovic & Vogt, 2021), which shows a positive association with corporate social responsibility. This study uses two proxies to measure the financial performance of firms; first is Tobin’s Q as market-based, and second is EPS as the accounting-based measure.

Environmental Performance

The environmental performance of the firms is mostly measured through carbon oxide emission and waste spills (Al-Tuwaijri et al., 2004; Trumpp & Guenther, 2017). The established data set such as Carbon Disclosure Project is frequently used from 2011 to 2015 to calculate the environmental performance by the scholars in the earlier studies (de Souza Leao et al., 2020; Kim, 2015; Matisoff et al., 2013; Stanny, 2013). The Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP, 2015) calculates the firms’ Environmental Performance by

measuring carbon footprints (Galletta et al., 2021). The EP is calculated using the content analysis method on composite EIndex presented by (Wellalage & Kumar, 2021). Composite indexes consist of air pollution control, energy management, water management, other pollution control measures, waste minimization and recycling energy, generation on-site, and carbon emission. The existence of the indicator of the EIndex is valued as 1; otherwise, 0.

Control Variables

Researchers frequently used firm size as a control variable in previous studies. Previous studies show different measures to calculate the firm size, but frequent measures for the firm size are the market value of equity, total sales, and total assets (Dang et al., 2018). Previous literature also shows that firm age is a frequently used control variable whose calculation is determined through the total number of years of the firms after its operation or being operated and filling of the firms done in the SEC. Although, researchers also find that a higher value of the firm age or existence of the firm from many years ago indicates the lower performance of the firm (Hannan & Freeman, 1984). The study used two control variables: the firm age and asset growth of the selected companies. Firm age is calculated by counting the total years the company has been operating after the commencement of its operation. The asset growth of the companies is determined through the opening total assets and subtracting the closing total assets then the calculated figure is divided by the closing total assets.

Definitions of Variables:

The following table II indicates definitions of the variables used in the study.

Table II. Definition of Variables

Variables	Definition	Authors
Corporate Social Responsibility (Independent Variable)	Corporate social responsibility can be described as economic, legal, ethical, and charitable responsibilities toward society. CSR refers to developing the right policy to fulfil social goals or values, describing the core responsibility of the organization.	(Kim et al., 2010) (Cho et al., 2012)
Financial Performance (Dependent Variable)	The firm's financial performance indicates its financial ability, which contributes to the marginal net benefit organization.	(Ishaq et al., 2021; Xiong et al., 2020)
(Moderating Variable)		
Environmental Performance	Environmental performance refers to an eco-friendly environment. It defines a process where splits and pollution are controlled to avoid environmental hazards.	(Jabbour et al., 2015; Neves et al., 2014)

Measurement of Variables:

Table III. Given below describes the measurement of variables.

Variable	Measurement	Author
CSR	Corporate social responsibility is measured through Five dimensions: employee, consumer, supplier, government, and society.	(Karaibrahimoglu, 2010)
EP	Composite EIndex is used based on 7 indicators for environmental management to measure environmental performance: air pollution control, energy management, water management, other pollution control measures, waste minimization, recycling energy, generation on-site, and carbon emission.	(Wellalage & Kumar, 2021)
FP	Financial performance is measured through Tobin's Q (market-based measure) and EPS which is accounting-based measure.	(Orlitzky et al., 2003)

4. Findings

Descriptive Statistics:

Descriptive statistics analysis is shown in Table II, which indicates total observations, standard deviation, mean values, and lowest and highest values of data. Standard deviation evaluates the dispersion from the mean where the highest value relates to more dispersion of data from the mean and vice versa. As shown in Table IV, descriptive statistics analysis of the data describes the total number of observations of Tobin's Q, EPS, firm age, EP, and assets growth is 350. The mean value of the firm age is 50.29, the highest value of the mean among all. While 0.162 is the lowest mean value of assets growth. The table below shows that 44.00 is the highest value of the standard deviation, which is the standard deviation value of EPS, and CSR specifies the lowermost value of standard deviation, which is 1.97.

Table IV. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Observations
EPS	24.25	44.00	-108.7	322.86	350
Tobin's Q	1.88	2.41	-0.15	23.04	350
CSR Disclosure	-6.98	1.97	-6.63	2.95	350
Assets growth	0.16	0.30	-0.60	5.00	350
Firm Age	50.29	33.07	4.00	215.00	350
EP	1.79	4.04	-4.46	20.92	350

Correlation Analysis:

A correlation is a statistical analysis that evaluates the connection between independent and dependent variables. The values of correlation range from +1 to -1, where positive values of the correlations analysis indicate the positive correlation between variables, which means the rise in one variable led to a rise in another variable. The negative value of correlation shows the negative correlation, which means both variables move in the opposite direction. An increase in the value of one variable leads to a decrease

in another variable, and a decrease in the value of one variable leads to an increase in another variable (Gujarati, 2009). Table V shows a negative correlation between an independent variable (CSR Disclosure) and the moderator variable (environmental performance), whose value is -0.62. The correlation between CSR Disclosure and EPS is positive, with a value of 0.01. In contrast, there is a negative correlation between CSR Disclosure and Tobin's Q, which means that an increase in CSR Disclosure would decrease the value of Tobin's Q.

Table V Correlational Analysis

Correlations	EPS	Tobin's Q	CSR Disc	EP	Assets growth	Firm Age
EPS	1.00					
Tobin's Q	0.26	1.00				
CSR Disc.	0.01	-0.11	1.00			
EP	0.04	0.05	-0.62	1.00		
Assets growth	0.04	-0.05	-0.09	0.05	1.00	
Firm Age	0.05	0.19	-0.20	0.11	-0.03	1.00

Robust Regression:

The following tables indicate the robustness check to see the correlation among CSR disclosure, EPS, and Tobin's Q and the simultaneous influence of CSR disclosure and environmental performance on EPS and Tobin's Q. We examined the association between CSR disclosure and FP using Stata software version 15.2.

As shown in Table VI, the robust regression indicates that CSR disclosure significantly affects EPS. The significant connection between CSR Disclosure & EPS is based on a 10% significance level with a 90% confidence interval. So, the P value shown in the table is 0.05 less than 0.10 (10%), indicating a significant association. Moreover, the result shows that if one unit of CSR Disclosure increases/decreases, it will change the 0.94 in the dependent variable (EPS). Additionally, coefficient values of the panel regression results of the CSR disclosure and EPS moving in the same direction show a positive direction.

Table VI. Regression Results of the Effect of CSR Disclosure on EPS

EPS	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[90% Conf.	Interval]
CSR Disc.	0.94	0.49	1.91	0.05	-0.02	1.91
Assets Growth	-0.39	3.16	-0.13	0.90	-6.61	5.82
Firm Age	0.26	0.02	8.91	0.00	0.20	0.32

As shown in Table VII, the robust regression indicates a significant association between the CSR disclosure (independent variable) and Tobin's Q. The significant

connection between CSR Disclosure & Tobin's Q is based on a 10% significance level with a 90% confidence interval. So, the P value shown in the table is 0.06, less than 0.10 (10%), indicating a significant association. Moreover, the result shows if one unit of CSR Disclosure increases/decreases, it will change the 0.041 in the dependent variable (Tobin's Q). Additionally, coefficient values of the panel regression analysis of the CSR disclosure and Tobin's Q move in the same direction.

Table VII. Regression Results of the Effect of CSR Disclosure on Tobin's Q

Tobin's Q	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[90% Conf.	Interval]
CSR Disc.	0.04	0.02	1.84	0.06	-0.00	0.08
Assets Growth	0.06	0.14	0.43	0.66	-0.22	0.34
Firm Age	0.00	0.00	2.95	0.00	0.00	0.00

As shown in Table VIII, the robust regression indicates a significant influence of environmental performance on the connection between CSR disclosure & EPS. The significant effect of environmental performance (EP) on the association between CSR Disclosure & EPS is based on a 10% significance level with a 90% confidence interval. So, the P value shown in the table is 0.09 less than 0.10 (10%), indicating a significant association. Moreover, the results indicate that CSR Disclosure & EPS significantly correlated using environmental performance as a moderator. The coefficient values of the panel regression analysis of the CSR disclosure and EPS also move in the same direction. The following table shows the simultaneous impact of Corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure & environmental performance on EPS.

Table VIII. Regression Results of the moderating effect of EP on CSR Disclosure and EPS

EPS	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[90% Conf.	Interval]
EP	0.46	0.28	1.87	0.09	0.09	1.01
CSR Disc.	1.54	0.61	2.50	0.01	0.33	2.75
Assets Growth	-0.57	3.10	-0.18	0.85	-6.68	5.53
Firm Age	0.26	0.02	9.04	0.00	0.20	0.32

As shown in Table IX, the robust regression indicates a significant influence of the environmental performance (moderator variable) on the relationship between the CSR disclosure and Tobin's Q. The significant influence of environmental performance on the association between CSR Disclosure and EPS is based on a 10% significance level with a 90% confidence interval. So, the P value shown in the table is 0.02 less than 0.10 (10%), indicating a significant association. Moreover, the result shows that CSR Disclosure and Tobin's Q significantly correlated using environmental performance as a moderator. Additionally, the coefficient values of the panel regression analysis of the independent variable (CSR disclosure) and dependent variable (Tobin's Q) also move in the same direction. The following table shows the simultaneous influence of Corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure & environmental performance on Tobin's Q.

Table IX. Regression Results of the moderating effect of EP on CSR Disclosure and Tobin's Q

Tobin's Q	Coef.	Std. Err.	t	P> t	[90% Conf. Interval]
EP	0.02	0.01	2.28	0.02	0.00 0.05
CSR Disc	0.07	0.02	2.70	0.00	0.02 0.13
Assets Growth	0.04	0.14	0.31	0.75	-0.23 0.32
Firm Age	0.00	0.00	2.81	0.00	0.00 0.01

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study contributes to the literature on CSR Disclosure by highlighting the relationship between CSR disclosure & FP. This is the first study that explores the moderating effect of environmental performance on the relationship between CSR Disclosure and Financial performance by covering manufacturing firms in Pakistan. Results of regression analysis indicate that a significant positive link between CSR Disclosure & Tobin's Q is consistent with the result of the previous study (Bhagat & Bolton, 2008; Garas & ElMassah, 2018). Furthermore, the findings of the study also indicate a positive correlation between CSR Disclosure and EPS, matching the results of the previous study (Lambertini & Tampieri, 2015). The result of the study shows that environmental performance significantly strengthens the link between CSR Disclosure and the firm performance of the manufacturing firms of the PXS 100 index consistent with (Mahmoudian et al., 2021; Qi et al., 2014; Tadros & Magnan, 2019; Uyar et al., 2020).

Although this study contributes to several works of literature, it faces some limitations that may be addressed by future researchers. Firstly, this study uses panel data from 2017 to 2021, covering a small time horizon for panel regression. Thus, further research on the link between CSR disclosure and FP may take 10 years as a time horizon for better regression analysis. This study only uses 100 index manufacturing firms that represent whole industries, which does not show an accurate representation of the whole industry. So, further research may also consider the whole industry. This study neglects the NGO as a stakeholder in measuring the independent variable (CSR disclosure), which leads to imprecision in measuring the CSR Disclosure. Moreover, future researchers may consider the role of bank lending as there is less literature considering the role of bank lending on the association between CSR Disclosure & FP.

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7. Appendices

Appendix: 1 List of the Sample Firms

Sr No.	Symbol	Name
1	ATLH	Atlas Honda Ltd
2	HCAR	Honda Atlas Cars (Pakistan) Ltd
3	INDU	Indus Motor Company Ltd
4	MTL	Millat Tractors Ltd
5	PSMC	Pak Suzuki Motor Co. Ltd
6	THALL	Thal Limited
7	PAEL	Pak Elektron Ltd
8	CHCC	Cherat Cement Co. Ltd.
9	DGKC	D.G. Khan Cement Co. Ltd.
10	FCCL	Fauji Cement Co. Ltd.
11	KOHC	Kohat Cement Co. Ltd.
12	LUCK	Lucky Cement Ltd
13	MLCF	Maple Leaf Cement Factory
14	PIOC	Pioneer Cement Ltd
15	JCL	Javedan Corporation Ltd
16	ARPL	Archroma Pakistan Ltd
17	COLG	Colgate-Palmolive (Pakistan)
18	EPCL	Engro Polymer & Chemicals
19	ICI	I. C. I. Pakistan Ltd
20	LOTCHEM	Lotte Chemical Pakistan Ltd
21	INIL	International Industries Ltd
22	ISL	International Steels Ltd
23	ASML	Aisha Steel Mill Ltd
24	MI&SI	Mughal Iron & Steel Industries
25	ENGRO	Engro Corporation Ltd
26	EFERT	Engro Fertilizers Ltd.
27	FATIMA	Fatima Fertilizer Company Ltd
28	FFC	Fauj Fertilizer Company Ltd
29	FFBQC	Fauji Fertilizer Bin Qasim Ltd
30	FCEPL	Frieslandcampina Engro Pakistan
31	MUREB	Murree Brewery Company
32	NATF	National Foods Ltd
33	NESTLE	Nestle Pakistan Ltd.
34	Unity	Unity Foods Limited
35	GHGL	Ghani Glass Ltd XD
36	TGIL	Tariq Glass Industries Ltd
37	SRVI	Service Industries Ltd.
38	MARI	Mari Petroleum Co. Ltd
39	OGDC	Oil & Gas Development Co. Ltd
40	POL	Pakistan Oilfields Ltd
41	PPL	Pakistan Petroleum Ltd
42	APL	Attock Petroleum Ltd

43	PSO	Pakistan State Oil Co. Ltd
44	SHEL	Shell (Pakistan) Ltd
45	SNGP	Sui Northern Gas Pipelines
46	PKGS	Packages Limited
47	CPBML	Century Paper & Board Mills Ltd
48	ABOT	Abbott Lab (Pakistan) Ltd.
49	AGP	AGP Limited
50	GLAXO	GlaxoSmithKline Pakistan
51	HINOON	Highnoon Laboratories Ltd
52	SEARL	The Searle Company Ltd.
53	HUBC	Hub Power Company Ltd
54	KEL	K-Electric Ltd
55	KAPCO	Kot Addu Power Company
56	ATRL	Attock Refinery Ltd
57	NFL	National Refinery Limited
58	NFL	Shakarganj Limited
59	IFL	Ibrahim Fibers Limited
60	ANL	Azgard Nine Ltd
61	GATM	Gul Ahmed Textile Mills Ltd
62	ILP	Interloop Limited
63	KTML	Kohinoor Textile Mills Ltd
64	NCL	Nishat (Chunian) Ltd
65	NML	Nishat Mills Ltd
66	GADT	Gadoon Textile Mills Ltd
67	YWML	Yousaf Weaving Mills Ltd
68	PAKT	Pakistan Tobacco Co.
69	POML	Punjab oil mills Ltd.
70	BNWM	Bannu Woollen Mills Ltd